

Zinc content in women of reproductive age with connective tissue dysplasia

Contenido de zinc en mujeres en edad reproductiva con displasia del tejido conectivo

96

Smirnova Tatyana Lvovna
PHD, (Medicine), Associate Professor of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of the 1Chuvash State University named after I. N. Ulyanov, address: 428034, 45. Moskovsky Avenue, Cheboksary, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0002-8224-1515; eLibrary SPIN-code: 8341-4307. e-mail: tismr@mail.ru

Sharapova Olga Viktorovna
MD, PhD, DSc., professor, the Head physician of the 2State Budgetary Institution of Healthcare "City clinical hospital of Vinogradov V.V." of the Moscow Healthcare Department, address: 117292, 61 Vavilova Str., Moscow, Russia.

MD, PhD, DSc., professor of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, 3Institute of Clinical Medicine of Federal State Autonomous Educational Institution of Higher Education I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation (Sechenovskiy University), address: 119435, 2 building, 4 Bolshaya Pirogovskaya Str., Moscow, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0003-0384-1705 eLibrary SPIN-код: 5786-6566, Author ID: 937365 e-mail: sharapova-olga59@mail.ru

Gerasimova Lyudmila Ivanovna
MD, DSc, prof., - Head of the educational and methodical office of the 2State Budgetary Institution of Healthcare "City clinical hospital of Vinogradov V.V." of the Moscow Healthcare Department, address: 117292, 61 Vavilova street, Moscow, Russia, Professor of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of the Medical Institute of Continuing Education of the 4Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Russian Biotechnological University» (FSBEU HE "ROSBIOOTEKH"), address: 125080, 11 Volokolamskoe highway, Moscow, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0002-3976-0934 Scopus ID: 57191171713 Researcher ID Web of Science: M-5260-2017 eLibrary SPIN: 7078-8406, Author ID: 629576 e-mail: profgera@mail.ru

Budnik Irina Vasilievna
MD, DSc, - Head of the head of the gynecological department of the 2State Budgetary Institution of Healthcare "City clinical hospital of Vinogradov V.V." of the Moscow Healthcare Department, address: 117292, 61 Vavilova street, Moscow, Russia, Head of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of the Medical Institute of Continuing Education of the 4Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "ROSBIOOTEKH", address: 125080, 11 Volokolamskoe highway, Moscow, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0002-9182-3250 eLibrary SPIN: 3023-1980, Author ID: 732137 e-mail: irina_budnik@bk.ru

Sitdikova Irina Dmitrievna
MD, DSc, prof., professor of 5Kazan Federal University, address: 420008, 18 Kremlevskaya Str., Kazan, Russia. DSc, Professor of the 6St. Petersburg State Pediatric Medical University, Russia, address: 941000, 2 Litovskaya Str., St. Petersburg, Russia. DSc, Professor of the 7Naberezhnye Chelny State Pedagogical University, Russia, address: 423806, 28 St. Nizametdinova, Naberezhnye Chelny, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0002-6835-402X Scopus ID: 6506943645 e-mail: sar1002@mail.ru

Zhuravleva Nadezhda Vladimirovna
PHD (Medicine), Associate Professor of the Internal Medicine Department of the 1Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "Chuvash State University named after I.N. Ulyanov", address: 428034, 45 Moskovsky Avenue, Cheboksary, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0001-6470-7724; eLibrary SPIN: 9314-2480. e-mail: zhuravlevanv@mail.ru

Ivanova Marina Konstantinovna
MD, DSc, prof., MD, professor of 8Izhevsk State Medical Academy, address: 426034, 281 Kommunarov Str., Izhevsk, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0002-4987-4127 e-mail: socol@mail.ru

Sannikova Julia Alexeevna
The student of 8Izhevsk State Medical Academy, address: 426034, 281 Kommunarov Str., Izhevsk, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0002-4265-5000 e-mail: slesareva_i@mail.ru

Colpakova Marina Vladimirovna
PhD, Associate Professor of the 7Naberezhnye Chelny Pedagogical University, address: 423806, 28 St. Nizametdinova, Naberezhnye Chelny, Russia. ORCID: 0000-0003-0854-3483 e-mail: Colpakovamarina10@gmail.com

Received: 12/20/2022 Accepted: 03/19/2023 Published: 04/25/2023 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8001892>

Abstract

The study of zinc content in hair in reproductive age women of the Chuvash Republic with connective tissue dysplasia aged 18-25 years was carried out. Comparing the content of zinc in the hair of reproductive age women with connective tissue dysplasia revealed a decrease in the content of zinc by a factor of 2.56. The ratio of zinc to iodine in women in the control group is 44.12, and in women with dysplasia it is 71, 17, which indicates the presence of an abnormal ratio of these elements.

Key words: connective tissue dysplasia, zinc, the ratio of zinc to iodine.

Resumen

Se llevó a cabo el estudio del contenido de zinc en el cabello en mujeres en edad reproductiva de la República de Chuvash con displasia del tejido conectivo de 18 a 25 años. La comparación del contenido de zinc en el cabello de mujeres en edad reproductiva con displasia del tejido conectivo reveló una disminución en el contenido de zinc por un factor de 2,56. La proporción de zinc a yodo en las mujeres del grupo control es de 44,12 y en las mujeres con displasia es de 71,17, lo que indica la presencia de una proporción anormal de estos elementos.

Palabras clave: displasia del tejido conjuntivo, zinc, proporción de zinc a yodo.

Hereditary disorders affecting the structure and function of connective tissue are a widespread pathology, the knowledge of the principles for making their diagnosis and treatment is necessary for specialists. Hereditary connective tissue disorders represent a heterogeneous group of monogenic disorders caused by genetic defects in the synthesis and / or breakdown of extracellular matrix proteins or by impaired connective tissue morphogenesis¹. Mutations in genes responsible for the synthesis and breakdown of the intercellular substance components are at the heart of the connective tissue dysplasia development. Considering that zinc, along with other elements, participates in the synthesis of collagen in connective tissue, it is necessary to determine the content of the element in the body of women with connective tissue dysplasia.

The study compared zinc content in hair of 120 reproductive age (18-25 years) women residing in the Chuvash Republic diagnosed with connective tissue dysplasia and in healthy women.

The collection of samples of the studied hair was carried out from the occipital region (methodology guidelines 4.1.1482-03, methodology guidelines 4.1.1483-03). The samples were placed in paper envelopes and stored in a dry place at room temperature.

In the study of hair samples, the accredited testing laboratory of ANO Center for Biotic Medicine, Moscow, Russia (ISO 9001: 2008 certificate 54Q10077 dated 05/21/2010) used methods of multielement analysis and atomic emission spectrometry, as well as inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP -AES and ICP-MS) (methodology guidelines 4.1.1482-03, methodology guidelines 4.1.1483-03).

Before mineralization, the collected hair samples for 10-15 minutes were treated with acetone (ultrapure, Khimmed, Russia), followed by three times rinsing with deionized water (18 MΩ * cm) obtained in a distiller with a combined membrane unit DVS-M / 1NA-1 (2) -L (Mediana-Filter, Russia).

After treatment, the hair was kept at a temperature of 60°C until their air-dry state.

Samples weighing about 0.05 g were mineralized in Teflon inserts in a Multiwave 3000 microwave sample preparation system (PerkinElmer - A. Paar, Austria), heated

using 5 ml of nitric acid (high purity grade, Khimmed, Russia) for 5 min, increasing the temperature to 200 ° C, then kept when reaching 200 ° C for 5 minutes, and then cooled to 45 ° C.

The samples obtained in this way were placed in polypropylene test tubes with a volume of 15 ml, while the Teflon liners and caps were treated three times with deionized water, and the lavage was sent to the corresponding test tubes.

The samples were brought to a volume of 15 ml with deionized water, and then, shaking in closed test tubes, they were thoroughly mixed.

The chemical elements, zinc and iodine, were determined in the hair samples using Optima 2000 DV (PerkinElmer, USA) and ELAN 9000 (PerkinElmer - SCIEX, Canada) spectrometers. The instruments were graded using PerkinElmer monoelement solutions.

The quality control of the study was carried out on the basis of the reference sample GBW03101 (Shanghai Nuclear Research Institute, China).

The obtained data were subjected to mathematical analysis using the software packages Microsoft Excel 2007 (Microsoft Corp., USA) and Statistica 6.0 (StatSoft Inc., USA) and using the methods of nonparametric statistics. The reference values used as standards in the ANO "Center for Biotic Medicine" are accepted as conditional biologically permissible levels (UBDU)².

Using the Student's test to prove the significance of the differences between the two populations, we calculated the critical two-sided t value and compared the critical t value with the calculated data from the table of the Student's parameter values at different levels of significance, while the results were assessed as statistically significant at p <0.05.

The statistical nonparametric U-test of Mann-Whitney inversions was used to evaluate the differences between two independent samples in terms of zinc levels measured quantitatively using an online calculator³.

The results of the study. Hair contains zinc, and its content is constant, unlike plasma. When comparing the zinc content in the hair of reproductive age women with connective tissue dysplasia, the zinc content was found to be decreased by the factor of 2.56 (table). The ratio of zinc to iodine in women of the control group is 44.12, and in women with dysplasia 71.17, which indicates the presence of an abnormal ratio of these elements.

Table 1. The content of chemical elements in the hair of the reproductive age women with connective tissue dysplasia residing in the Chuvash Republic, mg / kg (M±m)

Element	Element content in healthy women	Element content in women with connective tissue dysplasia	Evaluation of differences between groups according to the Mann-Whitney U-test	Reference values q25-q75
Zinc	92,74±2,49 p<0,05	71,7 ± 3,3 p<0,05	The differences are significant	94 – 183
Iodine	1,24±0,51	1,04 ±0,43	The differences are significant	0,42 – 2,7*

Note: Me-median, q25-lower quartile, q75-upper quartile; * - conditionally acceptable biological level

Zinc affects all processes occurring in the connective tissue associated both with the synthesis and breakdown of proteins. Zinc activates the enzymes of the metalloproteinase group that ensure cleavage of intercellular matter, in addition, zinc promotes the formation of phagocytes, increases the activity of macrophages, and ensures the accumulation of fibroblasts in the foci of inflammation. With the help of zinc, the deficiency of hyaluronic acid, which is a glycosaminoglycan of the amorphous substance in connective tissue, is replenished. Zinc is involved in activating the enzymes responsible for the processes of collagen biosynthesis. Zinc is a part of a number of enzymes: oxidoreductases, transferases, hydrolases, lyases, isomerases, ligases, the element's participation in the metabolism of fats, proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, and hormones has been proven ⁴. Excess of zinc was found to be an inhibitor of MMP-mediated collagen degradation in dentin ⁵.

Zinc absorption takes place in the duodenum, it is an active process and proceeds with the expenditure of ATP. In the blood plasma, 70% of zinc binds to albumins, 28% to α2-macroglobulins, a small part may be in a free form in the plasma. The main part of zinc is excreted by the kidneys, the rest with pancreatic juice, bile ⁶.

Zinc deficiency is observed in reproductive age women in Africa and in pregnant women ^{7, 8, 9}. Zinc deficiency carries a serious risk of complications during pregnancy and childbirth (the plasma zinc content in women with zinc deficiency was found to be 21.86 ± 7.21 versus 29.54 ± 7.62 mmol/L in women with normal zinc content, p<0.001) ⁹. It is necessary to provide pregnant women with a diversified diet in order to correct zinc deficiency ^{10, 11}. Zinc administration during pregnancy improves pro-

tection against malaria and reduces the risk of pregnancy complications ¹².

Zinc stabilizes the permeability of cellular and intracellular membranes and participates in mitosis, entering into a competitive relationship with cobalt ⁴. Zinc, entering into a competitive relationship with cadmium, copper and calcium, is absorbed in the small intestine ⁴.

In the body of an adult woman, zinc reserves are only 22.9-30.6 mmol (1.5-2 g), and skeletal muscles are the richest in zinc - they contain 62.6% of the total amount of the element. The optimal daily intake of zinc is 7.5-8.0 mg, and for pregnant and lactating women it reaches 12-15 mg, while 20-30% of the consumed compound is absorbed in the upper part of the small intestine.

A particularly high content of zinc in spermatozoa - up to 1900 µg / g - is explained by its influence on their motility and fertilizing properties.

Underdevelopment of otoliths in the inner ear in conditions of zinc deficiency leads to ataxia in newborns, impaired coordination of movements ⁴. Zinc provides differentiation of the cerebral cortex structures ¹³. Zinc deficiency results in the development of iron deficiency anemia, hepatosplenomegaly, dwarfism, hypogonadism, impaired puberty, and diabetes mellitus ^{14, 15}.

This is due to a decrease in the concentration of zinc in plasma, erythrocytes of the above patients. The appointment of zinc preparations is inevitable also for enteropathic acroderma.

Many pathological conditions of the liver are closely related to the level of zinc in the blood. Zinc suppresses liver fibrosis both by inhibiting the formation of collagen and by increasing the degradation of collagen, which was manifested by increased collagenase activity and increased levels of mRNA and MMP-13 protein ¹⁶.

Zinc deficiency negatively affects the synthesis of the retinol-binding protein, which provides transport of vitamin A in the blood, due to which there is a simultaneous deficiency of both factors.

The consequence of the outflow of endogenous, that is, undigested zinc by the body can be such congenital malformations of the fetus and newborn as hydrocephalus, micro- and anophthalmia, cleft palate, curvature of the spine, heart defects. Excessive excretion of this trace element can cause the development of a number of serious diseases. Impaired zinc metabolism is the cause of autosomal recessive hereditary enteropathic acrodermatitis. In sickle cell anemia with zincuria, pathological changes in zinc metabolism and disorders of glomerular filtration, tubular reabsorption are also noted. In medical practice, there are nutritional zinc deficiency and a deficiency associated with impaired absorption of this microelement - Prasad's disease, accompanied by severe iron deficiency anemia, short stature up to dwarfism, sexual

underdevelopment and other symptoms.

Disruption of zinc metabolism causes a number of adverse health effects in humans. However, the most pronounced negative effect of zinc deficiency has on the pregnant woman, fetus and newborn^{17, 18}. Zinc, as well as copper, ensures the normal formation of the fetal skeleton, therefore, even the borderline values of zinc significantly affect the future health of the newborn. In addition, it must be remembered that zinc is part of the hormone insulin, which stimulates the growth of the fetus. Zinc deficiency, defined as exogenous zinc deficiency in the post-natal period, is associated with nutritional deficiencies in pregnant women¹⁹. Zinc, together with other important trace elements, affects the activity of enzymes and the mechanical properties of connective tissue. In this regard, zinc deficiency disrupts the structure of collagen and affects the formation of a hernia. It has been proven that the appointment of zinc preparations to patients normalizes the exchange of copper and ceruloplasmin in pregnant women with Wilson-Konovalov disease²⁰.

Zinc is an important participant in many biochemical processes in cells, the most common intracellular element that affects the growth and differentiation of cells. As you know, the most zinc-rich cellular structures are erythrocytes, which may explain the frequent cases of anemia in women with connective tissue dysplasia.

Comparative analysis of the average level of zinc in the daily water-food rations of the population of the Chuvash Republic from the zone of ecological and biogeochemical optimum showed an intake of 14.3 ± 1.3 mg / day, compared to the ratio of 70.0 to iodine.

Based on the data of the study of the quantitative content of zinc in water in the optimum zone for the content of elements, 0.013-0.07 mg / l was established, the indicators in the disaster zone are 0.018-0.033 mg / l in different seasons, which confirms the fact that the population of the Chuvash Republic is deficient in zinc and needs medical correction.

Scientific works of V.L. Suslikov proved that the ratio of zinc / iodine in water in the zone of ecological and biogeochemical optimum in the Chuvash Republic reaches 6.0, while in the zone of ecological and biogeochemical disaster it is only 4.0 and is regarded as an abnormally unregulated ratio of elements²¹.

In a series of scientific publications, it is argued that up to 20-30% of zinc is absorbed from food, and the most valuable in this regard are meat, fish and pumpkin seeds, and in second place are eggs, cereals and beans that can satisfy the daily requirement for zinc, which is about 20 mg^{21, 22}.

According to the World Health Organization, more than 2 billion inhabitants of our planet suffer from problems

with the level of zinc in the body, and zinc deficiency is much more common than its excess. The reasons for zinc deficiency can be insufficient intake of it with food, the pathological influence of a number of microorganisms, Crohn's disease and other non-bacterial intestinal diseases, as well as a number of technogenic factors. It should be noted that most of the territory of Russia is characterized by endemic zinc deficiency, which is caused by an insufficient element's content in water and in the soil, including the Chuvash Republic^{2, 21}.

Conclusions

In women with connective tissue dysplasia, compared with the reference values, there was a significant decrease in zinc content in the hair ($p < 0.05$). Statistical analysis using the nonparametric U-test of Mann-Whitney inversions evaluated the differences between two independent samples, including women with connective tissue dysplasia and women with a physiological course of pregnancy, according to the level of zinc measured quantitatively using an online calculator. At $p < 0.01$, the value of the Mann Whitney U-test is 913.0 (99% of the sample values); at $p < 0.05$, the value of the Mann Whitney U-test is 1010.0 (95% of the sample values). According to the table for the selected level of statistical significance, a critical value of H1 was determined, indicating the presence of statistically significant differences between the groups $p < 0.01$.

We suggest that women with connective tissue dysplasia may have an endogenous deficiency of zinc and other essential trace elements. This requires supplementing the examination scheme of women with this pathology who are planning pregnancy with additional methods for studying the trace element spectrum and drug correction when detecting its changes in order to ensure a favorable course of pregnancy and the development of the intrauterine fetus.

References

1. Hereditary connective tissue disorders. Clinical guidelines. Moscow; 2009.
2. Skal'nyj A.V. Reference values of the concentration of chemical elements in hair, obtained by the ICP-ASP method (ANO Center for Biotic Medicine). *Microelements in Medicine*. 2003. 4(1):55-56.
3. Online calculator [Internet]. Mann-Whitney U-test [cited 2021 May 17]. Available from: https://www.eztests.xyz/criteria/mann_whitney.
4. Olivares M., Hertrampf E., Capurro M.T., Wegner D. Prevalence of anemia in elderly subjects living at home: role of micronutrient deficiency and inflammation. *European journal of clinical nutrition*. 2000. 54(11): 834-839. DOI: 10.1038/sj.ejcn.1601099.

5. Mehta J.V., Gajera S.B., Patel M.N. Antimalarial, antimicrobial, cytotoxic, DNA interaction and SOD like activities of tetrahedral copper (II) complexes. *Spectrochimica Acta. Part A, Molecular and biomolecular spectroscopy*. 2015; 136 Pt: 1881-1892. DOI: 10.1016/j.saa.2014.10.103.
6. Panchenko L.F., Maev I.V., Gurevich K.G. *Clinical biochemistry of trace elements*. Moscow: Federal State Budgetary Institution of Additional Professional Education "All-Russian Educational, Scientific and Methodological Center for Continuing Medical and Pharmaceutical Education" of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation; 2004. Russian.
7. Harika R., Faber M., Samuel F. et al. Micronutrient Status and Dietary Intake of Iron, Vitamin A, Iodine, Folate and Zinc in Women of Reproductive Age and Pregnant Women in Ethiopia, Kenya, Nigeria and South Africa: A Systematic Review of Data from 2005 to 2015. *Nutrients*. 2017. 9(10):1096. DOI: 10.3390/nu9101096.
8. Kocylowski R., Lewicka I., Grzesiak M. et al. Assessment of dietary intake and mineral status in pregnant women. *Archives of gynecology and obstetrics*. 2018. 297(6): 1433-1440. DOI: 10.1007/s00404-018-4744-2.
9. Iqbal S., Ali I, Rust P. et al. Selenium, Zinc and Manganese Status in Pregnant Women and Its Relation to Maternal and Child Complications. *Nutrients*. 2020. 12(3): 725. DOI: 10.3390/nu12030725.
10. Berhe K., Gebrearegay F., Gebremariam H. Prevalence and associated factors of zinc deficiency among pregnant women and children in Ethiopia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC public health*. 2019. 19(1): 1663. doi: 10.1186/s12889-019-7979-3.
11. Bailey RL, Pac SG, Fulgoni VL 3rd, Reidy KC, Catalano PM. Estimation of Total Usual Dietary Intakes of Pregnant Women in the United States. *JAMA network open*. 2019. 2 (6):e195967. DOI: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2019.5967.
12. Darling A.M., Mugusi F.M., Etheredge A.J. et al. Vitamin A and Zinc Supplementation among Pregnant Women to Prevent Placental Malaria: A Randomized, Double - Blind, Placebo-Controlled Trial in Tanzania. *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene*. 2017. 96(4):826-834. DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.16-0599.
13. Sarwar T., Zafaryab M., Husain M.A. et al. Redox cycling of endogenous copper by ferulic acid leads to cellular DNA breakage and consequent cell death: A putative cancer chemotherapy mechanism. *Toxicology and applied pharmacology*. 2015. 289(2): 251-261. DOI: 10.1016/j.taap.2015.09.018.
14. Marsh J.W., Djoko K.Y., McEwan A.G. et al. Copper (II)-bis (thiosemicarbazonato) complexes as anti-chlamydial agents. *Pathogens and diseases*. 2017. 75(7). DOI: 10.1093/femspd/ftx084.
15. Božić B., Korać J., Stanković D.M. et al. Mechanisms of redox interactions of bilirubin with copper and the effects of penicillamine. *Chemico-biological interactions*. 2017; 278: 129-134. DOI: 10.1016/j.cbi.2017.10.022.
16. Rehmani N., Zafar A., Arif H. et al. Copper-mediated DNA damage by the neurotransmitter dopamine and L-DOPA: A pro-oxidant mechanism. *Toxicology in vitro: an international journal published in association with BIBRA*. 2017; 40: 336-346. DOI: 10.1016/j.tiv.2017.01.020.
17. Rasic-Milutinovic Z., Jovanovic D., Bogdanovic G. et al. Potential Influence of Selenium, Copper, Zinc and Cadmium on L-Thyroxine Substitution in Patients with Hashimoto Thyroiditis and Hypothyroidism. *Experimental and clinical endocrinology and diabetes*. 2017. 125(2): 79-85. DOI: 10.1055/s-0042-116070.
18. Blasig S., Kühnen P., Schuette A. et al. Positive correlation of thyroid hormones and serum copper in children with congenital hypothyroidism. *Journal of trace elements in medicine and biology*. 2016; 37: 90-95. DOI: 10.1016/j.jtemb.2016.05.007.
19. Vimalraj S., Rajalakshmi S., Raj Preeth D. et al. Mixed-ligand copper (II) complex of quercetin regulate osteogenesis and angiogenesis. *Materials science and engineering. C, Materials for biological applications*. 2018; 83: 187-194. DOI: 10.1016/j.msec.2017.09.005.
20. Aspli K.T., Flaten T.P., Roos P.M. et al. Iron and copper in progressive demyelination--New lessons from Skogholt's disease. *Journal of trace elements in medicine and biology*. 2015; 31: 183-187. DOI: 10.1016/j.jtemb.2014.12.002.
21. Suslikov V.L. *Geochemical ecology of diseases: in four volumes. Vol. 4: Atherosclerosis*. - Cheboksary: Publishing House of the Chuvash State University; 2011. Russian.
22. Gromova O.A., Torshin I.Yu., Tetruashvili N.K. et al. On new trends in nutritional support for pregnancy. *Obstetrics and gynecology*. 2018. 1: 21-28. Russian.